

An Assessment of Drivers and Dynamics of 2020 Sino-Indian Border Conflict

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 27, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 29, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : China, CPEC, Galwan Valley, Jammu and Kashmir, Ladakh, Territorial Dispute.</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7101805</p>	<p><i>The territorial conflict between India and China in the disputed region of Jammu and Kashmir (J&K) has a protracted and complex history. In 2020, Indian and Chinese soldiers clashed violently following the territorial disagreements in eastern Ladakh in J&K. The conflict resulted in stalemate over troops disengagement at the Line of Actual Control (LAC) with increasing militarisation of the border dispute. Amid the standoff, Beijing reinforced its positions at multiple locations in eastern Ladakh. This article argues that China's approach to the border conflict is shaped by India's move of changing the status of Ladakh in August 2019, infrastructure build-up in the strategic territory in the disputed region, New Delhi's opposition to China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), growing Sino-Indian rivalry and China's considerations over its reputation at global level. The article finds that Beijing's assertive action in eastern Ladakh has enabled it to address its security concerns and territorial vulnerabilities in the disputed border region. For Pakistan, the standoff helps advance its security interests and undermine India's hegemonic designs in the region.</i></p>

Introduction

Geo-strategic environment of South Asia and relationship among Pakistan, China and India has been structured in the backdrop of territorial disagreement particularly in the disputed region of Jammu and Kashmir (J&K). The three states have overlapping claims on different territories in the region for which India has pursued an aggressive approach (Khan, 2021). The long-standing territorial disagreement and border conflict between India and China in J&K has a complex history. The conflict dates back to Sino-Indian war in 1962, following which Chinese seized Aksai Chin plateau in the northwest of Ladakh in the disputed region. The 'uneasy truce' following the war established 3,380 kilometres (km) long undefined, loosely demarcated line, referred to as the Line of Actual Control (LAC). However, disagreement over the position of LAC remains a bone of contention between the two states. Several rounds of talks between China and India in the last three decades have failed to resolve the boundary dispute and the tensions have occasionally led to brawls (Zargar, 2020). In early May 2020, Chinese troops advanced in eastern Ladakh to halt Indian advances and encroachments on China's territory. Chinese People's Liberation Army (PLA) and Indian soldiers got engaged in skirmishes along the LAC when both sides accused each other of trespassing. The conflict reached its apex on June 15, 2020, when a skirmish in the Galwan valley in eastern Ladakh resulted in 20 deaths on the Indian side and 4 Chinese casualties (Anbarasan, 2021). China and India have endured several tense clashes since 1962 war, but these were the first combat fatalities on the LAC since 1975. Though both sides agreed to withdraw troops from the border in February 2021 (Tarapore, 2021), the disengagement process has been deadlocked since August 2021 and both sides still have deployed 50,000-60,000 soldiers each in Ladakh theatre (Vasudeva, 2021). Meanwhile, PLA has consolidated its position on strategic heights in border areas including Galwan, Depsang Plains and Hot Springs with military buildings and permanent structures. Regardless of how disengagement progresses, the conflict cast a shadow over bilateral relationship between the two states.

Sino-Indian border dispute generates important questions to ponder. First, what are the drivers of Sino-Indian conflict in eastern Ladakh and what led China to take an assertive action at the LAC? Second, what are the implications of this conflict for Pakistan? The answers to these questions are important and point to political, economic and strategic context of territorial disputes as well as the current state of Sino-Indian competition and political antagonism between the two states.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In post-Cold War era, many ethnic and nationalist conflicts are closely linked to territorial disputes and affect global conflict behaviour. A territorial dispute may become a "foundational threat" to the security of a state since "nation-states comprise well-defined and controlled areas." Keeping in view that territory is a "basic element" of a state's composition, the state's leadership will be "more willing" to use force during a territorial disagreement (Senese, 2005). Arguably, many scholars consider territory an important source of conflict most

likely to push states towards war (Holsti, 1991; Luard, 1970; Vasquez, 1993). Siverson and Starr (1991) note that geographic contiguity significantly contributes towards the diffusion or spread of conflict. According to Goodhand (2018), territorial disputes involve a wide range of factors that may include competition over resources and power relations between neighbouring states. Mancini (2013) comments that cultural, economic and political motives coupled with “nationalist reading of sovereignty” can cause conflict over contested territory. Huth (1996) argues that a number of attributes can increase the likelihood of a militarized territorial and border conflict such as a stalemate in negotiations, shared ethnic connections with a bordering minority or group, or attempts by the target state to alter the status quo. Hensel (1998) claims that a longer history of armed conflict and failed nonviolent attempts to resolve the territorial and border dispute is likely to increase the militarized conflict of nature. Hensel highlights that territorial dispute is more likely to evolve into an enduring geopolitical rivalry. In this context, the militarized territorial conflict in South Asia, involving Islamabad, Beijing and New Delhi is strategically significant, leading to geopolitical rivalries not only between Pakistan and India but also between China and India.

Hensel (2000) describes that territory is considered important for three reasons: First, many territories may be seen as important for their tangible contents or attributes. i.e., they contain valuable resources or provide access to trade routes or control over strategic waterways. Territory is also seen strategically important as it is tied to a state’s security and power and contains “defensible geographic features.” Second, a territory is significant because of psychological appeal or intangible attributes or it may be linked to national cohesion and autonomy of a state or its strategic and economic significance. From this perspective, Aksai Chin is considered important because of its tangible and intangible attributes as this plateau contribute to China’s security, national defence and power. Third, territory can be considered highly salient because of reputation. In that sense, relinquishing the territory to an adversary is seen as a weakness and other rival states might push for their own demands on territorial claims or other issues. Hensel quotes Schelling to emphasize this point:

“What is in dispute is usually not the issue of the moment, but everyone’s expectations about how a participant will behave in the future. To yield may be to signal that one can be expected to yield...”

Avis (2020) argues that the causes of a territorial dispute are a state’s desire to maximise its power, claimed “rights” to a territory on the basis of history, ethnicity or geography and national or global politics for reasons of diverting attention from existing issues. From Realists point of view, territory is “a fundamental power base” and emerging powers will adopt aggressive postures toward contested territories. Accordingly, changing power dynamics lead to intensifying confrontations over control of contested territory. In this context, China, an emerging power, has adopted an assertive posture toward territorial dispute in the disputed region of J&K. In the light of above discussion, a framework is developed to assess the drivers of the Sino-Indian conflict in 2020. This *framework* emphasizes that the 2020 Sino-Indian dispute involves a multitude of factors as mentioned in Table 1.

S. No.	Drivers of Conflict
1	China’s territorial claims on the basis of history and geography
2	China’s sovereignty concerns
3	Concerns over Strategic territories in Ladakh
4	Security of China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC)
5	Sino-Indian Rivalry
6	China’s reputation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. China’s Territorial Claimson the basis of History and Geography

China’s conflict with New Delhi is the result of Beijing’s territorial claims on Ladakh as part of Tibet. The history of Western Tibet is closely connected and interwoven with Ladakh (Nath, 2016). In China’s views, Tibet came under Chinese jurisdiction during the Yuan Dynasty in mid-thirteenth Century and was inherited by the governments of the Republic of China and the People’s Republic of China (Liu, 2020). The India-China boundary is generally divided into three sectors— The middle sector has no serious disputes; in the Western sector, Ladakh borders Xinjiang and Tibet and the border dispute pertains to Johnson’s Line whose legality was never accepted by China. In the Eastern sector, **McMahon Line** was proposed by British officials at Simla conference in 1914. It runs from Bhutan to Myanmar, separating Tibet from Sikkim and Arunachal Pradesh (Valdameri, 2020) but the Chinese officials refused to sign the Simla Agreement and China disputed the legality of the Tibetan representative’s signature, asserting that “Tibetan government was not a sovereign” (Wei, 2019, p. 62). It is important to note that British attempts to define the border of British India with China influenced India’s claim in the Western sector (Zargar, 2020). Prior to 1947, Britain sought Tibetan independence and continually attempted Tibet to leave China. India’s first Premier Jawaharlal Nehru was deeply impressed by this British thinking. Throughout the 1950s, Nehru worked continuously to turn Tibet into a “buffer zone” between

China and India and considered that move important to establish Indian hegemony over South Asia (Garver, 2006, p. 129). In response, Beijing started to consolidate its position in the Aksai Chin through the development of a road that was a strategic communication link between Tibet and Xinjiang known as China's National Highway (NH 219 / G 219). When, in 1958, New Delhi became aware of this Highway, Indian troops were ordered to implement the "Forward Policy" by establishing forward outposts and "increasingly provocative and aggressive patrolling" along the contested border (Wei, 2019). In 1959, India "supported the Tibetan rebels," against China, granted asylum to the Dalai Lama and advanced claims on Aksai Chin. Beijing saw Nehru's aggressive approach as Indian attempts to "seize Tibet" (Garver, 2006, p. 90)

It is worth noting that China made concerted efforts to settle the boundary dispute through negotiations. Chinese premier **Zhou Enlai** and Nehru met in Delhi from 20 to 25 April 1960. However, the negotiations failed completely due to New Delhi's inflexibility over territory claims. Over the next two and half years, relations between India and China reached a low ebb with Indian army continued its aggressive forward posturing in the disputed areas, and PLA fortified its positions as a response, resulting in small scuffles in border region. On October 20, 1962, the PLA eventually decided to launch a massive offensive both in Ladakh and Arunachal Pradesh (Sidhu & Yuan, 2003, pp. 14-15). On achieving its objectives and defeating Indian army, China announced a unilateral ceasefire on November 20, 1962 (Sandhu, 2020). In fact, in Western sector, China believed it had secured all strategic areas required for the security of NH 219 and vacated all additional territories. However, Chinese troops also withdrawn from some areas in Ladakh that could give Indian army access to Aksai Chin (Panag, 2020). In 1993, India and China concluded an agreement which acknowledged the LAC as the functional boundary. This was followed by efforts to demilitarise the border conflict by establishing guidelines for their soldiers to follow in the subsequent Agreements and Protocols (Sandhu, 2020; Westcott, 2021) as shown in Table 1.

However, despite these agreements both states maintained "irreconcilable positions" over the location of the LAC (Westcott, 2021). Beijing accepts the LAC of November 7, 1959 and New Delhi insists on the LAC of September 8, 1962. China's claim on the territory between the two LACs was precisely the cause of the 1962 war (Sun, 2020). Beijing believed that the territories vacated by its troops following 1962 ceasefire have been re-occupied by Indian soldiers, a move which increased China's suspicion of Indian motives (Liu, 2020) and led to 2020 strife along the LAC.

S.No.	Date	Agreements
1	September 1993	"Agreement on the Maintenance of Peace and Tranquility along the Line of Actual Control"
2	November 1996	"Confidence Building Measures in the Military Field along the Line of Actual Control in the India-China Border Areas"
3	April 2005	"Political Parameters and Guiding Principles for the Settlement of the India-China Boundary Question"
4	January 2012	"Establishment of a Working Mechanism for Consultation and Coordination on India-China Border Affairs"
5	October 2013	"The Agreement between India and China on Border Defence Cooperation"

Source: Adopted from Sandhu. (2020, July 21). It is time to accept how badly India misread Chinese intentions in 1962 – and 2020. *The Wire*.
<https://thewire.in/security/india-china-xi-jinping-lac-border-modi-1962-war>

2. China's Sovereignty Concerns

An important factor that triggered Galwan valley clash is described as India's move of revoking Article 370 of its Constitution on August 5, 2019 that granted autonomy to the disputed State of J&K and illegally bifurcated it into two federally administered Union Territories (UT): J&K and Ladakh. This decision, which New Delhi described as "strictly an internal matter," is in complete disregard to "bilateral understandings" reached with Islamabad (Simla Agreement 1972) and Beijing (1993, 1996, 2005, 2012 & 2013) as well as United Nations (UN) Resolutions that have established the State of J&K as "disputed territory" (Haider, 2020). The Ladakh UT included the disputed Western sector and Chinese controlled Aksai Chin which offers the only direct road link through NH 219 between Xinjiang and Tibet. Aksai Chin is vital to Chinese control of its entire western frontier as Beijing will have to rely on NH 219 for access in case of conflict in Xinjiang or Tibet, which are home to its ethnic minorities (Sun, 2020). Worst still, on August 6, 2019, Indian Minister of Home Affairs, Amit Shah in his remarks in Parliament described Aksai Chin and Pakistan controlled Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK) and Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) as "occupied" and stressed that "We will get them, and you will see this in future" (Ramakrishnan, 2020). *India's move and provocative statements of its leaders led to worries in*

China that New Delhi harbours “irredentist ambitions towards Aksai Chin” and *trying to unilaterally change the status quo along the border* (Westcott, 2021). China strongly protested the revocation of Article 370 and the Chinese Foreign Ministry spokesperson remarked:

“China is always opposed to India’s inclusion of the Chinese territory in the western sector of the China-India boundary into its administrative jurisdiction. This firm and consistent position remains unchanged. Recently India has continued to undermine China’s territorial sovereignty by unilaterally changing its domestic law. Such practice is unacceptable and will not come into force.”

The spokesperson urged India to “strictly abide by relevant agreements concluded between the two sides and avoid taking any move that may further complicate the boundary question” (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2019). China also called for a private meeting to discuss Kashmir at UN Security Council (UNSC) on August 16, 2019. After the informal consultations, the Chinese envoy said that there was a “general will” of UNSC members that parties should not take “unilateral actions” (Mitra, 2019). The situation was further complicated with New Delhi’s issuance of maps showing AJK, GB and Aksai Chin as part of India. Again, in October 2019, the Chinese Foreign Ministry stressed that by “placing part of Chinese territory under Indian administration,” New Delhi was harming Beijing’s “sovereign rights and interests.” Fravel (2020) notes that China embraced a more strident approach to sovereignty since Xi Jinping became the General Secretary of the Chinese Communist Party. In 2013, Xi linked sovereignty with the realization of his “China dream,” declaring in 2016 that “no foreign country should expect” Beijing “to swallow the bitter fruit” of harm to our “national sovereignty.” In July 2014, President Xi underscored the need for early resolution of boundary dispute in a meeting with India’s Prime Minister Modi in Brazil. This point was also emphasized during his visit to India in September 2014, reflecting that China is growingly concerned over sovereignty issues since President Xi came to power (Sandhu, 2020). In July 2021, Xi visited Tibet and vowed to “strengthen infrastructure construction” along the LAC to “defend the territory and build the homeland.” According to an analyst, the visit was intended to signal to India that Xi “places the border struggle with India close to the very top of China’s national agenda” (“China’s Xi Vows,” 2021).

Several observers have acknowledged that the revocation of Article 370 may have triggered the current border conflict in Galwan. A Chinese expert, Dr. Wang Shida at the China Institutes of Contemporary International Relations, noted that India’s unilateral move has “posed a challenge to the sovereignty of Pakistan and China and made the India-Pakistan relations and China-India relations more complex.” Shida argued that India by incorporating territories “under the local jurisdiction of Xinjiang and Tibet” into its Ladakh UT and placing AJK within its “so-called union territories” of J&K, “forced China into the Kashmir dispute” and “dramatically increased the difficulty in resolving the border issue between China and India” (Shida, 2020). India’s former Ambassador to Bhutan, China and Pakistan, Gautam Bambawale noted: “One cannot discount that the [Chinese] actions are guided by concerns regarding the Indian UTs” of J&K and Ladakh.” (Haidar, 2020). Korybco (2020) concurred with this analysis by saying that Indian Home Minister’s “reaffirmation” of New Delhi’s claims to Aksai Chin “triggered” China’s “threat perception of India.” Against this backdrop, China’s assertive action along the LAC in 2020 is described by an analyst as “one-plus retaliation”, implying that Beijing responds to India’s unprovoked aggression by advancing its own position one step further than its rival has (Chubb, 2021).

3. Concerns over Strategic Territory and Highways

A major cause of the Sino-India border clash appears to have been India’s infrastructure development in Ladakh which threatened China’s strategic territories in the disputed border areas including NH 219. In 2005, India announced a project of 61 roads covering 3,417 km near the LAC. The road infrastructure is expected to complete by December 2022 and will wear away China’s traditional infrastructure advantage (Singh, 2019). One of the most important highway of the project is the 250km Darbuk–Shyok–Daulat Beg Oldie (DS-DBO) road which runs adjacent to the LAC and links Leh (capital of Ladakh) to Karakoram Pass (Haidar, 2020). The DBO is strategically situated between Gilgit-Baltistan in the west, Shaks gam area (under China’s control) in the north and Aksai Chin in the east. The DBO is the highest airfield in the world, just 9 km of Aksai Chin and 10 km from the Karakoram Pass [Figure 1].

Figure 1

Sino-Indian Border Confrontations in Ladakh in June 2020

Note: Dhalde et al. (2020). India-China border clash explained. <https://multimedia.scmp.com/infographics/news/world/article/3091480/China-India-border-dispute/index.html>

Construction of Bailey bridges and branch roads from the DS-DBO highway enable Indian troops to get behind the Chinese defences via 8 mountain spurs or 'Fingers' along the northern bank of the Pangong Lake, threatening Chinese control of NH 219. Moreover, the DS-DBO road is a "game changer" as it cuts down the time taken for forward deployments of Indian forces to Indian airbase in Daulat Beg Oldie (DBO) from two days to just six hours (Bhadrakumar, 2020). Against this backdrop, Beijing was alarmed that DS-DBO road would give New Delhi access to strategic heights from where Indian troops could target NH 219, severing Xinjiang connection with Tibet (Sawhney, 2020; Bhadrakumar, 2020). In a well-calculated move, PLA has positioned itself in Depsang Plains, Galwan valley and Pangong Lake. Chinese buildup was also observed in the area of Hot Springs and Demchok (Panag, 2020). Following the June 15 skirmish, an official of China's Ministry of National Defense declared that Beijing has sovereignty over entire Galwan valley. Blaming Indian army for incursions into Chinese territory, the official said, "The responsibility lies entirely with India" (Wu & Myers, 2020). Undoubtedly, China's actions across the LAC bolstered its strategic ability particularly control of heights at 'fingers' 4 to 8 of Pangong Lake provides PLA access to dominate the DS-DBO road and pre-empt any Indian operations which could threaten Aksai Chin and NH 219 (Shah, 2020).

A former Indian Army officer noted that Beijing's political aim is "to maintain the 'status quo' along the LAC on its own terms, which is to forestall any threat, however remote, to Aksai Chin and NH 219" (Panag, 2020). China has also been concerned that DS-DBO poses a threat to Karakoram Highway. From this perspective, China has consolidated its position over strategic heights and thwarted Indian options of an assault from Depsang Plains towards Karakoram Highway and Xinjiang, the only gateway available to India to Central Asia (Shah, 2020). This argument is supported by the Chinese fortifications in the Depsang which in case of any conflict

“will aid China’s ‘salami-slicing tactics’ by connecting it with the Karakoram Pass” for strategic advantages (Ahluwalia, 2020).

4. Security of CPEC

China is also uneasy over the security implications of DS-DBO road for CPEC, a flagship project of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)—unveiled by President Xi in 2013. The CPEC starting point is in Xinjiang, crosses Pakistan’s Gilgit-Baltistan region and advances onward to the Arabian Sea port of Gwadar. The Corridor would enable Beijing to *bypass* the narrow *Malacca Strait* to reduce the time and cost of transportation of its seaborne imports. India has strongly opposed CPEC on grounds of the corridor running through GB, the territory claimed by India. Given that New Delhi also included GB in Ladakh UT, Beijing perceived that Indian troops pose threats to Karakoram Highway from DBO airbase and DS-DBO road (Maqsood, 2020). India’s opposition to CPEC and its aggressive claims on AJK and GB —through which CPEC passes— only feeds China’s suspicion that India wants to undermine CPEC because BRI is seen as a challenge to Delhi’s strategic interests in South Asia.

In this context, China’s strategic advance into Depsang Plains near Karakoram Pass secures access route to Central Asia as well as CPEC. Furthermore, Galwan valley is also close to the Siachen Glacier, which Indian forces occupied in 1984. Siachen, the highest-elevation battlefield on Earth, has been the scene of a decades-long stand-off between New Delhi and Islamabad. By occupying the Glacier, India gained strategic advantage over Pakistan as well as the ability to observe Chinese controlled Shaksgam valley (Bokhari, 2020). Against this backdrop, the DS-DBO road allow India to bring troops, arms and equipment to its posts in the Siachen (Rakisits, 2020). Chinese forward positions in Galwan valley and Pangong Lake provide PLA a strategic advantage to cut off DS-DBO road and thereby deny access to Occupied Siachen or Karakoram Highway. These positions at strategic heights not only permit PLA to launch in offensive operations but also offer Beijing and Islamabad “a classic pincer move” to trap Indian military in “the Triangle of LAC formed by GB, Aksai Chin and Indian Occupied Ladakh” (Naureen & Waqar, 2020).

5. Sino-Indian Rivalry

The Indo-Pacific strategy report published by the US in 2019 is of great significance in the context of Sino-Indian border conflict. The Indo-Pacific strategy confirmed China as the “biggest competitor” and Indo-Pacific region as “one of the most critical regions for the future for the US.” The strategy describes New Delhi as a key partner in the containment approach towards Beijing. In China’s view, India “being emboldened by its strategic alignment with Washington,” is pursuing aggressive and hostile policies in the region (Korkmaz, 2020). Beijing sees India as a part of the US (and its allies) strategy to contain China which has intensified Sino-Indian rivalry (Sun, 2020). India is a member of Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad) – a group that includes the US, Australia and Japan—to contain China, in the guise of promotion of a free and open Indo-Pacific. In addition, New Delhi and Washington declared a “comprehensive global strategic partnership” following President Trump’s visit to India in February 2019 (Korybco, 2020). The visit also followed by a \$3 billion arms sale to India (Korkmaz, 2020). Chinese leadership views growing Indo-US ties as the greatest potential threat to Beijing’s ambitions in South and East Asia. Certainly, the border conflict emphasizes the importance of growing US-India relationship. Bhadrakumar (2020) notes India’s ‘forward policy’ in eastern Ladakh was developed after signing of the US-Indian nuclear agreement in 2008 and resulted in overall ‘militarization’ of India’s foreign policy. With the strengthening of Indo-US partnership and growing strategic competition between US and China, the conviction developed in New Delhi that “a muscular approach towards China becomes sustainable.” This belief contributed significantly to co-relate India’s foreign policy to alliance with Washington. No doubt, Indian militarised foreign policy fits well in American agenda to strengthen its strategic partnership with New Delhi—one driven in great part by a shared concern about China. On June 1, 2020, US representative Eliot Engel, the House Foreign Affairs Committee Chair, expressed concern over “ongoing Chinese aggression” on the LAC. On June 2, US President Donald Trump discussed the border confrontation during a phone conversation with India’s Premier Modi. These “high-level US interventions” on Sino-Indian border conflict underline the growing US-China competition (Kugelman, 2020). Besides, these interventions also emphasize US strategy that it wants New Delhi to counter Beijing. According to a leading Chinese expert **Feng (2020)**:

“The continuous rapprochement of the US and India has reinforced India’s hardliners in their psychological attitudes towards China, who believe that China will avoid conflict with India. They sense an opportunity on the border issue,...presenting the possibility for the Indian government to build sensitive facilities in sensitive places at a sensitive time, regardless of the Chinese government’s concerns. The actions of India directly caused the bloody conflict.”

New Delhi's increased collaboration with Washington, is pushing it to achieve its hegemony in South Asia and engage China into conflicts to threaten its strategic interests particularly its economic partnerships. Arguably, China has acted to secure its perceived interests in Ladakh. Many experts believe China's response to India's provocations on the LAC would protect the Chinese BRI investment in South Asia and help Islamabad to secure its economic and strategic interests in GB (Khan, 2020).

6. Reputation

Beijing sees territory in Ladakh highly important because of China's reputation and international prestige. China's defence of its territorial integrity accelerated India's "pro-American pivot," but Beijing remained committed to not relinquish its territory in the face of India's US-backed offensive. In Beijing's calculations, doing so could be seen as China's weakness and could have "catalysed a chain reaction of coordinated provocations" of rival states in the South China Sea, causing Beijing to lose the initiative in the region and perhaps never overcome the 'strategic setback' (Korybko, 2020). It is important to note that Ambassador Alice Wells, Principal Deputy Assistant Secretary of State for South and Central Asian Affairs in her public statement criticized Beijing's actions on border with India and linked them with China's "provocations" in South China Sea (Kugelman, 2020). Furthermore, India has also sided with US on issues related to China's sovereignty and security which include bolstering ties with Taiwan, expressing concerns and voicing support to protests in Hong Kong and harbouring government in exile of Tibet. The standoff sent a signal to India to "desist from anti-Chinese policies" and transgressions (Shah, 2021). In Beijing's view, Indian troops re-occupied the vacant areas in Ladakh due to exploitation of China's vulnerabilities during Covid-19 (Sun, 2020). An assertive action to advance into the territory secured in 1962 war thus, became an imperative from reputation perspective. For China, to yield to Indian advances in Ladakh may indicate to surrender to its rivals in South Asia and Indo-Pacific.

Implications for Pakistan

1. For Pakistan, Sino-Indian conflict is a "strategic balancer" that has greater potential of keeping India engaged, especially if Beijing and Delhi feel little incentives to resolve the conflict. The intention of both sides to assert power and protect territories where "even grass doesn't grow" is likely to see surge in operational military costs (Siddiqi, 2020). That would be a strategic benefit for Islamabad because in operational terms, Indian Army have to significantly strengthen its military footprint causing the diversion of military assets from LOC/Indian occupied J&K to LAC and thereby reducing India's force capability to make any military move into AJK & GB (Rakisits, 2020). In December 2020, India's Strike Corps which was dedicated for launching offensive in Pakistan—was reportedly deployed to operate across LAC in Ladakh. This re-tasking of the 1 Corps is indeed a "significant erosion" in Indian army's "slim local quantitative advantage over Pakistan" (Tarapore, 2021).
2. From military operational perspective, by overlooking the DS-DBO road leading to airbase in DBO, PLA has effectively blocked any Indian assault towards Siachen or GB. Arguably, Pakistan's position at Siachen has been fortified (Shah, 2020). A former Pakistan army officer observed that strategically Chinese infrastructure in Ladakh provides a "relief to Islamabad as Indian forces will face difficulty to make further thrust into Siachen Glacier and Kargil ("China Marginalised India," 2020). According to a regional expert, the Chinese fortifications seek to dominate DS-DBO road and will strengthen Pakistan defenses along the LOC (personal communication, with B. Shah, June 17, 2021)
3. India's removal of J&K special status has put Kashmir back on the "international radar" with Beijing emerging as a disputant in the conflict. These two outcomes are welcome news for Pakistan (Rakisits, 2020).
4. Since CPEC is the the flagship project of BRI, military and strategic interaction at political level between China and Pakistan is inbuilt into it. According to Pravin Sawhney, an Indian defence analyst, abrogation of Article 370 and the subsequent border conflict has strengthened this "unique relationship." Given, that security of the CPEC against Indian threat is of paramount importance, Beijing has put talks on the Galwan valley off the diplomatic table. In this scenario, Pakistan army and PLA joint assault in Northern Ladakh to "provide depth to the CPEC" cannot be dismissed (Javeed, 2020).
5. The border conflict helps advance Pakistan's core objective which is to deter Indian hegemony in South Asia and Indian Ocean Region (IOR). India's subdued response to China's assertive action in Galwan valley brawl has dented India's reputation as bulwark to China in the Indo-Pacific region. Tarapore (2021) comments that New Delhi is likely to reduce budget for Indian Navy and defer naval modernization as it needs to bolster its conventional defenses along the LAC with China. India is already considering a 175-

ship navy instead of a 200-ship one, and it may abandon its plans for a third aircraft carrier to save money. Such steps would weaken India's ability to compete strategically with China and may worry India's partners in the Quad as they seek maritime cooperation to counterbalance Chinese Navy in IOR.

CONCLUSION

China's assertive action in eastern Ladakh was guided by its desire to protect its sovereignty and territorial integrity and to safeguard its strategic and economic interests from 'unprovoked' Indian aggression. Given the growing rivalry, distrust and hostility, the militarised territorial dispute could become a distinct factor in Sino-Indian relations with increasing possibility of a war breaking out between the two states in near future. For Pakistan, the standoff has produced political, economic and strategic benefits. Moreover, China's assertive action in eastern Ladakh provides an opportunity for Islamabad to secure CPEC route and fortify its position at Siachen, GB and along the Line of Control in J&K as the Chinese military pressure will keep Indian military engaged along the LAC.

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